

Blossoms of Heritage

Advocating for Malta's
Threatened Flora

Project Documentation by Abigail Farrugia GRD 6.1A

Ideation

The first step for this project was to come up with some ideas. The ideas I came up with are the following:

Idea 1: Creating posters educating the public on the main causes of species endangerment. These posters will have a tactile twist to them. Poster 1)Habitat loss: This poster could use a combination of graffiti and bits of concrete for tactility, which will represent the effects of overdevelopment. 2)Pollution: This poster can have a trash collage (candy wrappers, can parts etc) representing our neglect of the natural environment. 3)Exploitation of wildlife: This poster will consist of an animal sitting on a shelf with red stitches on its side showing that it has been poached.

Idea 2: A series of tiles with designs of local wildflowers/fauna to educate locals on local species of fauna (if possible, using threatened species). This project can be executed by creating digital patterns of the plants using geometric shapes and then printing them on a ceramic tile (or other collaterals). Then it can also be created by creating the tiles from scratch by moulding each flower into a square tile of ceramics and giving them a glossy finish. On the back of each tile will be some information on the flower such as some history, its threats and how people can help along with the flower's name. (Just like we preserve our culture we should preserve our wildflowers too. Tiles will be used for this project for multiple factors. Firstly, a tile is a material which arouses curiosity, secondly, the material is just as fragile as these small and delicate wildflowers. Thirdly, tiles being a symbol of Maltese heritage and culture they would be a perfect medium to remind the public to keep wildflowers in our culture by preserving them. Using culture as a motivator in this campaign will help drive the message to my target audience as both locals and expats have an interest in culture. This product can also be used as a method to raise funds by reproducing the designs and selling them.

Idea 3: Creating infographic posters on some endangered species in Malta. Each poster containing some basic information on the species, how it became endangered and what can be done to help protect the species. Infographics will be used as they are shareable and can simplify complex information, making it accessible to a wider audience. This campaign can also have sticker packs for messaging apps and social media that feature endangered animals and conservation slogans. Using stickers will be a fun way for people to express their support for the cause.

Idea 4: A roll-the-dice board game on environmental problems related to species. The game has positive and bad actions with consequences reflecting each of them. The game is played by rolling the dice, moving spaces according to the number on the die and according to where you land you either stay, move forward or backwards. These actions and consequences will help users understand the impact that small actions can have. It will also further enrich people with ideas of how to help conserve local species.

Planning

After planning out some concepts I decided to sketch out some thumbnails as seen in image 1. The next step was to choose an idea. Here I decided to go with the idea of creating tiles with Maltese flowers. Around this time, I come across the website www.maltawildplants.com and through this site, I found out that locally we have quite a few endangered plant species. Thus, I decided to focus my Project on that. After some thorough research, I picked 6 threatened local species and decided to use them for my Project. For the selection process, I made sure every species selected has a threatened status by checking the Red Data Book. The selected species were the Maltese Rock-Centaury, the Maltese Everlasting, the Maltese Cliff Orache, the Southern Tulip, the Woody Catchfly and the Large-flowered Sawfly Orchid.

Image 1: Project ideas sketches

Creation

The first thing I did after selecting the plants was, sketch out their basic features in my journal. After that I collected a few images of local tiles as inspiration which can be seen in image 8. Next, I created a few design ideas for each flower as seen in images 2 to 7. After that, I started the digitization process where I continued experimenting with the designs. I found it a bit challenging to turn my designs into the style of Maltese tiles. To overcome this struggle, I created some sketches of some local tile designs, examined them, and noted down the main structure and features of each design as seen in image 13. Through this exercise, I found a tile whose basic layout could be adapted to my work, and I used its elements as a foundation of my work as seen in image 14. After that, I experimented a bit with a few of my designs until I reached a design which I was satisfied with.

Image 2: The Maltese Rock-Centaury sketches

Image 3: The Maltese Everlasting sketches

Image 4: The Maltese Cliff Orache sketches

Image 5: The Southern Tulip sketches

Image 6: The Woody Catchfly sketches

Image 7: The Large-flowered Sawfly Orchid sketches

Image 8: Some Traditional Maltese Tiles

Images 9, 10, 11, 12: Southern Tulip digital experimentation

Image 13: Maltese tiles rough sketches with annotations

Image 14: The Maltese Everlasting sketches

When working digitally I organised my work in different steps. In the first step, I created all the basic details in greyscale. In the second step, I added details to each artwork. Then in my third step, I added colour and in my final step, I refined everything including colours. When it comes to colours I tried matching the colours to photographs of the actual flowers as seen in image 17.

Image 15: Basic designs in greyscale

Image 16: Design with details in greyscale

Image 17: Extracting colours from images and applying colour

Image 18: Tile designs finishing touches

The way I structured the tiles was, I used a bird's eye view of each plant's flower at the centre of each design and then used the plants' side view at the tiles' corners. Each design had different colours even if some plant's colours looked similar. This was done to create a sense of individuality and uniqueness to each plant as no plant was like the other. Something I also did was use parts of the plant's design but at a larger scale for the shape of the tiles' corners to give each tile a sense of harmony.

Image 19: Using parts of the design for the tile's corners

Image 20: Playing around with layout and colours

Image 21: Old versions of the final designs

Once all the designs were done, I moved on to creating the postcards. The first thing I did to create these postcards was to research postcard sizes and designs for inspiration. Throughout this process, I found a postcard I had of BirdLife Malta which I used as my main reference for the postcards' layout. After this, I created some sketches to plan out how the front and back of each postcard will look, as can be seen in image 22. Afterwards, I moved to the digitization process where I laid out the tile designs next to each other forming a pattern on the back and added some relevant information I put together on a Word document on the front. For the information, I decided to include a few facts on each plant along with a brief description of my project. Regarding the postcard's design, I wanted to go for a traditional postcard layout.

Image 22: Planning the postcards and artwork sizes

After finishing my postcards' design, I got some advice on how I could improve my design by removing some unnecessary information and keeping the design minimal. It was also suggested to me to delve away from the traditional postcard design and go for a simpler approach, but I decided not to do so as I wanted my whole project to have a traditional feel. These changes can be seen in images Thus, I made a few adjustments but kept the same layout. On this postcard, I included the name of my design pages on social media so people can follow my work. I also wrote down who the sponsor for this project is but decided not to include their logo as it would clash with the postcards' design and colours.

Images 25: Postcard pattern

Images 23 & 24: BirdLife Malta Postcard

Maltese Cliff Orache Bjanka tal-Irdum

Confined to sheer cliffs in the southwest of Malta and west of Gozo and the General's Rock (Hagret il-Ġeneral), this plant is endemic to Malta and is also rare. This species is extremely ancient, having most likely survived the Ice Ages only on the Maltese Islands. This species is classified as Critically Endangered mostly because of habitat loss, introduction of alien species. Laws on a national and international level protect this species.

The Endangered Tiles project was created as a reminder that just like our traditional Maltese tiles, our local plant species are part of our heritage and thus we must conserve them.

Dear card holder,

Share this card on your social media and pass it on to spread awareness.

Love,
Abigail Farrugia

Images 26: Initial postcard design

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The Blossoms of Heritage project was created as a reminder that just like our traditional Maltese tiles, our local plant species are part of our heritage and must be protected. Share this card on your social media and pass it on to spread awareness.

Sponsored by Gozo Graphics

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Image 27: 2nd postcard design after feedback

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Image 28: Final postcard design

Image 29: Tiles Mockup

Image 30: Postcard mockup

Image 31: Sawfly Orchid & Southern Tulip Tiles

Image 33: Maltese Cliff Orache & Woody Catchfly Tiles

Image 32: Maltese Everlasting & Maltese Rock-centaury Tiles

